

Let's tell stories of change: the value of Storytelling

What is the best way to inspire others and get them to take action too? Tell them your story of change! To enhance its effect, apply the Storytelling technique: the art of storytelling with a focus on conveying emotions.

How do you work with storytelling to make the information more impactful? How do you tell stories that are easy to remember? How do you get something to move the receiver to action? When undertaking a DFC process, skills such as empathy, creativity and teamwork are developed, which are essential for storytelling, i.e. to tell a story that is engaging and creates a bond with the audience, connecting with their emotions.

Before starting to tell the story, it is advisable to take certain parameters into account:

- **Structure:** design the beginning, the development, the climax and the ending (introduction, middle and end).

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- **Situation:** the story is told objectively and answers the "6 W's of journalism": what, who, where, when, why and how.
- **Length:** the story should be between 2 and 3 pages long.
- Type of narration:
- **First person:** this allows the storyteller to be identified with the listener. It is testimonial, based on empathy.
- **Third person:** it relates facts told as objective experiences. This type of narration is ideal for presenting the solutions that have been created.
- Once these criteria have been defined, what aspects are fundamental to use the art of Storytelling applied to each of the DFC phases?

FEELING PHASE

1. **Beginning:** Choosing a topic (framework) that is relevant to both the project developers and the people who will benefit from the solution.

QUESTIONS TO ASK: What is the purpose of telling this story? What is the essence? What is the content?

2. **Protagonists:** Those who tell the story itself and also the beneficiaries of the solutions, on whom the audience projects itself in order to make sense of the story. Including emotions makes the audience empathize with the protagonists.

QUESTIONS TO ASK: Why can or should the audience care? Can we create a story that reflects the "heart" of the protagonists?

3. **Information** (obtained in the "Gain Understanding" step): The story, in order to be understandable to the audience, needs to show some details, thus increasing authenticity and bringing certainty to the context.

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QUESTIONS TO ASK: What is the context, what experiences and emotions does it convey?

END OF PHASE FEEL AND BEGINNING OF PHASE IMAGINE

4. **Defining the challenge** (How could we...?) and **Brainstorming:** This is the moment to create intrigue and suspense. You can use, for example, the procrastination technique: manage time to produce emotions in the audience.
5. **Prototyping:** A space for entertainment, where the hands are occupied and the mind is freed. With this "breath of fresh air" the audience is given a period to relax.

PHASE ACT

6. **Conflict or climax:** Show the problem that the protagonists of the story are going to solve and how they do it.

EVOLUTION PHASE

7. **Reflection:** The protagonists evaluate their process to give it a personal meaning from their own context, experience and perspective; thus, they evolve. It is useful to collect moments in the process that have brought about change and with which the audience can identify, as they are part of the common pattern of human growth.

QUESTIONS TO ASK: Is the story honest, coherent and credible? In contrast to the generalised attitude of hiding mistakes, DFC is committed to showing them, in order to learn from them, so don't hesitate to tell them in your story so that the public can also learn from your experience.

SHARE PHASE

8. **End:** The story needs to have an end that is fully connected to the beginning of the story; it should not only allow the audience to identify with and feel part of the story, but also invite them to recreate their own story.

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QUESTIONS TO ASK YOURSELF: What do I hope to achieve with the story?

And if you want to **further enrich your story of change**, some extra resources:

- At the beginning of the story you need to establish a **state of equilibrium**. Then include a **trigger** that breaks it, so that little by little the story becomes more complicated and the **denouement** arrives. In this way, the viewer's attention is held. It is important to work on the beginning and the end, as these are the parts that are most remembered.
- **Anchor points:** The story can be linked to stories or sayings, to evoke other stories or social legitimacy that are recognised by the audience and reflect universal values.
- **Metaphor:** Ideal when the idea or concept is complex. This brings reality closer to the audience and makes it easier to understand.

We invite you to share your stories to offer an "extension" of the created universe, which will serve as an inspiration to others, who can apply your solution and improve it, adapt it, scale it...

Come and tell stories of change to keep improving the world!

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